

Self-Efficacy and Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers in Relation to their Job Performance

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Abstract:

The question of what makes a good teacher posits the goal of this paper to know whether teachers' effectiveness and resilience determine their job performance. In this premise, this study examines whether teachers' effectiveness and resilience influence their job performance. Using a descriptive research design, data were collected from 98 Junior High School Teachers through a validated and reliable researcher-made questionnaire. Research ethics protocol, including informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality, were strictly observed. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze respondents' profiles, while Mann-Whitney U Test and Spearman Rho determined comparative and relational analyses. Findings revealed significant differences in self-efficacy and resiliency based on sex and income, with female teachers and those with higher incomes demonstrating greater efficiency and resilience. A positive correlation was found between self-efficacy, resilience, and job performance. These results suggest that educational institutions should invest in programs that enhance teachers' efficacy and resilience to improve job performance.

Keywords: Job performance, junior high school, resiliency, self-efficacy, teachers.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Teachers play a crucial role in the educational system, influencing student outcomes through their efficacy and resilience. Research suggests that psychological characteristics contribute to teaching effectiveness, with instructional delivery, skills development, and behavior modification being key factors in evaluating a teacher's performance. While some educators maintain strict classroom structures, others adopt more flexible, creativity-driven approaches. A critical aspect of teacher performance is self-efficacy, derived from Bandura's social-cognitive theory, which posits that belief in one's abilities affects effort and persistence in problem-solving situations. Understanding these elements can help identify strategies to enhance teacher effectiveness (Kim, 2018; McGuire, 2018; Djigic, 2015).

Resilience is essential for teachers to navigate the challenges of the evolving education system, as it involves utilizing personal and contextual resources to maintain commitment, enthusiasm, and well-being (Beltman, 2015). Factors such as the work environment, attitudes, and social dynamics significantly impact teacher performance, which is a key determinant of student achievement. Policymakers seeking to improve education should prioritize teachers, as they are the system's primary resource. Observations reveal that some educators struggle with exhaustion due to limited support and the inability to sustain their energy, often leading to misrepresentations that do not reflect their true identities or capabilities.

The researcher also sees a significant reduction in teachers' feelings of purpose, morale, and attendance. Some teachers exert less effort and tend to feel disoriented in their sense of drive to meet the required tasks due to multiple workloads. Moreover, tardiness and teacher absenteeism were concerns during faculty meetings, School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions, and focus group discussions (FGD). The researcher's motivation for doing this study came from these first-hand experiences and observations.

Current State of Knowledge

Teacher efficacy refers to educators' belief in their ability to influence student learning, with Khanshan (2020) identifying two dimensions: internal efficacy, reflecting confidence in teaching skills, and external efficacy, emphasizing external factors like socio-economic status. Teachers with high self-efficacy, particularly younger ones, are more likely to integrate technology into their instruction (Scherer, Siddiq, & Tondeur, 2019). However, studies

on the relationship between age and self-efficacy show mixed results—some highlight experience and adaptability as key factors, while others find no significant age-related effects. Research also suggests that age influences teachers' confidence in using ICT (Šabić, Baranović, & Rogošić, 2021). In the Philippine education system, rapid changes, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, have tested teachers' self-efficacy, increasing stress and anxiety (Malagisic et al., 2021). Professional development in instructional strategies enhances self-efficacy, with continuous skill development, such as online training, playing a crucial role in maintaining teachers' confidence and effectiveness (Entegro, 2022).

Research on the relationship between age and teachers' self-efficacy has yielded mixed results. Ghanizadeh and Moafian (2019) found that older teachers tend to have higher confidence in their self-efficacy, while Klassen and Tze (2014) highlighted its growing significance in school psychology. However, a study by Odanga and Aloka (2024) in Kenya found no statistically significant impact of age on teachers' self-efficacy, particularly in classroom management. Teaching experience, rather than age, has been shown to influence self-efficacy, with Hafner (2024) identifying years in the profession as a predictor of confidence in classroom management and teaching methods. Additionally, the UNESCO report (2021) emphasized that moonlighting negatively affects teacher efficacy, as taking on extra jobs to supplement income leads to physical and mental exhaustion, ultimately reducing classroom performance and student engagement.

Resilience plays a crucial role in teachers' dedication and efficacy, enabling them to navigate the emotional demands of the profession (Lacaba, Lacaba, & Caliwan, 2020). Teacher well-being is influenced by personal characteristics, motivation, and commitment to their institution, with success-oriented individuals experiencing higher resilience (Martin, 2017). A study in Zambales, Philippines, found that factors such as adequate facilities, administrative support, and a positive work environment contribute to better teaching performance and resilience (Duplon, Ventura, & Decena, 2022). Additionally, teachers' attitudes toward their profession significantly impact their resilience, as positive perspectives strengthen their ability to cope, while negative beliefs may weaken it. Addressing these attitudinal challenges through professional development and support networks can enhance teachers' resilience and overall effectiveness (Lacaba, Lacaba, & Caliwan, 2020).

Teaching is one of the most intellectually, emotionally, and socially demanding professions, requiring educators to master subject knowledge, instructional strategies, and resilience in the face of challenges (Mercer, 2020; Sikma, 2021). As the pillars of society, teachers must manage both educational and psychological demands, emphasizing the need to prioritize teacher well-being through positive psychology (MacIntyre & Mercer, 2014). Their mental health significantly influences classroom dynamics, yet many face stress, burnout, and attrition, particularly within the first five years, known as the "vulnerability period," when 40–50% leave due to high workloads, limited support, and classroom management difficulties (Gallant & Riley, 2014; Kelly et al., 2018). Economic challenges further test their resilience, but coping mechanisms enhance adaptability, focus, and decision-making under stress (Zhang & Luo, 2023). Research highlights that self-efficacy, resilience, and emotion regulation are crucial in preventing burnout and maintaining effectiveness despite financial and professional pressures (Li, 2023). Additionally, studies suggest that male teachers exhibit higher resilience, correlating with lower stress and burnout levels, as seen in research on pre-service physical education teachers (Melguizo-Ibáñez et al., 2023).

Teachers' job performance, defined as their contribution to achieving educational goals, is influenced by instructional, professional, and personal qualities, as well as classroom management and teaching strategies (Özdemir & Gören, 2017; Ali & Haider, 2017). Sociodemographic factors like experience, gender, age, and educational background also play a role, emphasizing the need to consider these in teacher development programs (Kotherja & Hamzallari, 2022). A study in Misamis Occidental found that job satisfaction strongly correlates with performance, with supervision and job security as key predictors (Baluyos, Rivera, & Baluyos, 2019). The Teachers Strengths and Needs Assessment (TSNA), aligned with the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS), evaluates teacher performance, with DepEd programs ensuring alignment with competency standards. While educational attainment, service length, and salary grade do not significantly impact 21st-century skills and job performance, younger teachers are more technologically adept due to globalization (Albano, 2021). Research suggests that job satisfaction and high teaching performance enhance resilience, with social support and motivation being crucial factors (Abarro, 2018; Ambion, 2023). Additionally, while educational attainment and training attendance significantly improve teaching performance, experience and position do not, highlighting the importance of continuous professional development (Batangas, 2022).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded in three key theories: Albert Bandura's (1977) Self-Efficacy Theory, Norman Garmezy's research on resilience, and Don Elger's (2007) Theory of Performance. Bandura's self-efficacy theory highlights an individual's belief in their ability to perform tasks, influencing motivation, behavior, and goal attainment. In education, teacher self-efficacy plays a crucial role in instructional effectiveness, job satisfaction, and stress management. Teachers with strong self-efficacy are better equipped to maintain classroom discipline, utilize

resources effectively, and support student learning. Understanding the antecedents of self-efficacy can enhance teacher well-being and improve overall school effectiveness (Gonzaga, 2020; Barni, Danioni, & Benevene, 2019). Resilience, as conceptualized by Garmezy, refers to an individual's ability to thrive despite adversity through protective factors like self-control, resourcefulness, and purpose. In teaching, resilience acts as a psychological safeguard, enabling educators to manage stress and adapt to challenges (Baylon, 2020; Taylor, 2013). Elger's Theory of Performance further explains that performance improvement depends on factors such as knowledge, skills, identity, and environment. Teachers, as performers, guide students by fostering engagement and reflective practices, ultimately driving learning and application. These theories collectively provide a framework for understanding how self-efficacy and resilience influence teacher effectiveness and professional growth (Leasure, 2018).

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the self-efficacy and resiliency of Junior High School Teachers regarding their job performance in a Public Secondary School, large Division, Central Philippines for the School Year 2021-2022. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: 1) the level of self-efficacy of junior high school teachers in the area of instructional delivery, skills development and behavior modification; 2) the level of resilience of junior high school teachers in the area of work environment, attitudinal concerns and social environment; 3) the level of Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers; 4) the significant relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy and the level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers; 5) the significant relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy and the level of Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers; and 6) the significant relationship between the level of Resiliency and Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers.

Methodology:

This section presents the research design, the subject and respondents of the study, the research instrument, the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the procedure, analytical schemes, and the statistical treatment in data analysis.

Research Design

This study aims to determine the level of self-efficacy and resiliency of Junior High School teachers in relation to their Job Performance in a Public Secondary School, a large Division, in Central Philippines for the School Year 2021-2022. Hence, the descriptive research design is employed. According to Vega (2015), this design describes the status of an event, people, or subjects as they exist. It usually makes some comparison, contrast, and correlation. This study aims to describe the level of self-efficacy and resiliency of Junior High School (JHS) teachers in relation to their job performance. Likewise, it seeks to compare and correlate the respondents' responses on the mentioned aspects. Thus, the descriptive design is appropriate for this study. A survey is also essential to a descriptive research design because the researcher gets to know the things that specifically affect them. The researcher utilizes a survey questionnaire to prove the value of facts and in focusing attention on the most important things to be reported.

Study Respondents

The respondents of this study were 98 Junior High School (JHS) teachers in a Public Secondary School, a large division, Central Philippines, for the School Year 2021-2022.

Instruments

The research instrument consisted of three parts: the respondents' profile, a self-made questionnaire on self-efficacy, and a resiliency questionnaire. The self-efficacy section covered Instructional Delivery, Skills Development, and Behavioral Modification, with responses interpreted on a five-point scale ranging from "very high level" (4.50–5.00) to "very low level" (1.00–1.49). The resiliency questionnaire assessed Work Environment, Attitudinal Concerns, and Social Environment, using a similar five-point scale. Additionally, the study utilized the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for evaluating teachers' performance during the 2021-2022 school year. The IPCRF, an assessment tool for government employees, rates teachers' accomplishments based on Key Result Areas (KRAs) such as Instructional Competence, Professional Growth, Learning Outcomes, Community Involvement, and Special Tasks, which must include at least 15 objectives (Lopez, 2019). The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.85-excellent) and reliability (for self-efficacy is 0.933 and for resiliency is 0.940 both interpreted as excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

As soon as the validity and reliability of the instrument are established, permission from the Division Superintendent of Negros Occidental, the District Supervisor, and the School Heads to administer the questionnaire to the Junior High School Teachers in the District of Manapla will be sought. Upon approval, copies of the questionnaire will be

reproduced and personally distributed by the researcher to the respondents, enabling him to explain the purpose of the study.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of self-efficacy of junior high school teachers in the following areas: Instructional delivery, skills development, and behavior modification. Descriptive.

Objective No. 2 utilized a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers according to the following areas: Work Environment, Attitudinal Concerns, and Social Environment.

Objective No. 3 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers.

Objective No. 4 used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman Rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy and the level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers. This scheme was used to determine the relationships between pairs of variables (Frankenfield, 2019).

Objective No. 5 used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman Rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy and the level of Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers.

Objective No. 6 used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman Rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of resilience and Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher has supervised the preparation and implementation of the study to ensure that ethical considerations are followed correctly. To maintain the anonymity of the raw data, the respondents' identity and responses to the data-gathering instrument were kept confidential. Furthermore, all related literature in this study was adequately cited and acknowledged in the references.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Level of Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Teachers According to Instructional Delivery

Instructional Delivery Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>		
1. can perform a thorough evaluation of the class performance.	4.48	High level
2. discuss topics that motivate and are fascinating to students.	4.54	Very high level
3. employ classroom discipline effectively.	4.46	High level
4. I use different teaching strategies to suit my students' learning needs.	4.46	High level
5. provide varied explanations to questions asked by my students.	4.55	Very high level
6. provide varied instructional materials and topics in my class.	4.38	High level
7. possess a mastery of the subject matter.	4.63	Very high level
Overall Mean	4.50	Very high level

Table 1 shows the level of self-efficacy of Junior High school teachers according to instructional delivery; the overall mean score is 4.50, which is interpreted as a "very high level." The examination of statistics has shown that three out of seven items obtained a mean score, which is interpreted as "very high level," and four out of seven items, which indicates a "high level" of self-efficacy in terms of instructional delivery.

Item No. 7, which states "possess a mastery of the subject matter," obtained the highest mean score of 4.63, interpreted as "very high level." In contrast, Item No. 6, which states, "provide varied instructional materials and topics in my class," got the lowest mean score of 4.38, interpreted as "high level."

This implies that the junior high school teachers demonstrate expertise in the subject matter. However, challenges for teachers arise to keep students' interest for a longer span or in what they do in the classroom since instructional materials cannot be maximized due to the school's limited technological facilities.

According to the Department of Education (2017), in today's continuously growing diversity of students in the classroom, including higher accountability standards, teachers in the present era may find their jobs even more challenging. Specifically, the education reform process warrants an equivalent supportive focus on teacher quality – high-quality teachers who are properly equipped and prepared to assume the roles and functions of a K to 12 teacher.

Table 2
Level of Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Teachers According to Skills Development

Skills Development Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>		
1. can identify the various learning styles of my students.	4.43	High level
2. can determine the difficulties of my students in the class.	4.45	High level
3. can assess the mental capabilities of my students.	4.44	High level
4. assist students in performing their class activities.	4.54	Very high level
5. <u>can</u> identify the different learning capabilities of my students.	4.45	High level
6. assist students in meeting the class assignments and projects.	4.31	High level
7. provide opportunities for my students to participate in class discussions and activities.	4.56	Very high level
Overall Mean	4.45	High level

Table 2 reveals the level of self-efficacy of junior high school teachers according to skills development; the overall mean score is 4.45, which is interpreted as a "high" level. The examination of statistics in Table 4 shows that two out of seven items obtained a mean score of a "very high level" of self-efficacy in terms of Skills Development, and the remaining four items obtained mean scores that were interpreted as a "high level" of self-efficacy.

Item no. 7, which states, "provide opportunities to my students to participate in class discussion and activities," obtained the highest mean score of 4.56, while item no. 6, which states, "assist students in meeting the class assignments and projects," got the lowest mean score of 4.31 which is interpreted as "high level."

The findings indicate that teachers encourage students to take an active part in the activities and discussions that take place in the classroom. Even though teachers have achieved a high degree of self-efficacy in terms of skills development, it is still difficult for teachers to keep students efficient in meeting the deadlines of their class assignments and projects.

Teachers are essential in guiding students through tasks and assignments to ensure that they understand the material at a deep level rather than just memorizing facts. According to Gu et al. (2016), teacher efficacy implies teachers' beliefs about their ability to teach skills in such a way as to lead learners to achieve their learning goals. It involves the judgment of the individual teacher's strength in helping students to be reminded most of the time of their tasks.

Table 3
Level of Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Teachers According to Behavior Modification

Behavior Modification Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>		
1. can maintain the learning interest of my students during the class.	4.47	High level
2. can manage learning behavior problems constructively.	4.40	High level
3. can demonstrate to students my commitment to obtaining good conduct.	4.60	Very high level
4. encourage my students to participate in class discussions and activities.	4.68	Very high level
5. can maintain order in class.	4.53	Very high level
6. go out of my way to get as much information as possible to provide interesting topics to my students.	4.31	High level
7. employ classroom discipline effectively.	4.55	Very high level
Overall Mean	4.50	Very high level

Table 3, Level of Self-Efficacy of Junior High School Teachers according to Behavior Modification obtained an overall mean score of 4.50, which is interpreted as a "very high level."

Item No. 4, which states "encourage my students to participate in class discussion and activities," obtained the highest mean score of 4.68, interpreted as "very high level." In contrast, item no. 6, which states, "go out of my way to get as much information as possible to provide interesting topics to my students," got the lowest mean score of 4.31, interpreted as "high level."

About teachers' behavior modification, this evidence implies that the Junior High school level teachers set clear routines for classroom activities, set expectations to students to let them know what is expected of them. However, some teachers tend not to go the extra mile to get more information, interesting topics, or meaning, to be more resourceful because they set for the traditional teaching method.

Demirdag (2015) stated in his research that teachers' self-efficacy is not only a strong indicator of their capabilities, but it also plays a vital role in shaping the behavior and achievement of students. Researchers suggest that self-efficacy affects both students' motivation and teachers' teaching strategies and critical thinking. In addition, research shows that individuals with low levels of self-efficacy may negatively influence both teachers' teaching methods and students' behaviors and engagement.

Considerable research by Caprara et al. (2013) has shown that teachers with high levels of self-efficacy experience higher levels of job satisfaction, lower levels of job-related stress, and face less difficulties in dealing with students' misbehaviors. Thus, understanding the main antecedents of self-efficacy may have significant payoffs in working for teachers' well-being and school effectiveness and improvement.

Table 4

Level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers According to Work Environment

Work Environment Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships.	4.30	High level
2. feel like I am part of the team (shared mission, values, efforts, and goals).	4.47	High level
3. am encouraged to solve as many of my work-related problems as possible.	4.41	High level
4. believe in and take pride in my work and my workplace.	4.44	High level
5. am accepted for the person I am.	4.60	Very high level
6. can motivate myself to learn and teach when I need to.	4.52	Very high level
7. feel safe and secure in my workplace.	4.44	High level
Overall Mean	4.45	High level

The statistical investigation of Table 4 shows the overall mean score of 4.45, which is interpreted as a "high level" in the level of resiliency of Junior High school teachers according to the work environment.

It reveals that two out of seven items obtained mean scores, which indicate "very high level" in terms of Work Environment, and the remaining five obtained mean scores, which indicate "high level."

Item no. 5, "I am accepted for the person I am," obtained the highest mean score of 4.60, interpreted as "very high level,." In contrast, item no. 1, "I tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships," obtained the mean score of 4.30, which is interpreted as "high level."

Item no. 1, "I tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.30, which is not bad after all since it is still interpreted as "high level," meaning teachers can still manage to perform even under recovery. The resiliency of the Junior High school teachers can have a positive impact on student outcomes.

Lacaba, Lacaba, and Calivan (2020) conducted a case study that concentrated on how teachers' resilience affected their dedication and efficacy in the classroom. The study clarified that teaching is an emotionally demanding profession and that sustained dedication and efficacy require resilience. The study highlights how teachers must become resilient to handle the emotional demands of their work.

Table 5

Level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers According to Attitudinal Concerns

Attitudinal Concerns Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. <u>am able to</u> embrace when changes occur.	4.55	Very high level
2. am not easily discouraged by failures.	4.44	High level
3. try to see the lighter side of things when facing difficulties.	4.54	Very high level
4. can cope with stress and make me stronger.	4.41	High level
5. stay focused and think <u>even</u> I'm under pressure.	4.35	High level
6. consider several alternatives to a problem before I make decisions.	4.49	High level
7. set a specific goal before I begin a task.	4.58	Very high level
Overall Mean	4.48	High level

The statistical investigation of Table 5 reveals the resiliency of the Junior High School Teachers according to Attitudinal Concerns. The overall mean obtained is 4.48, which is interpreted as "high level."

It shows that three out of seven items obtained a mean score, which indicates "very high level" in terms of Attitudinal Concerns, and the remaining four obtained mean scores, which indicate "high level."

Item no. 7, "I set a specific goal before I begin a task," obtained the highest mean score of 4.58, which is interpreted as "very high level,." In contrast, item no. 5, "I stay focused and think even I'm under pressure," obtained a mean score of 4.35, which is interpreted as "high level."

This implies that teachers can stay focused and perform even under pressure. They can still perform better, if not the best, just for the students to get the quality education they need.

However, in reality, there emerge numerous challenges and setbacks in teaching which cause teachers' attrition, demotivation, stress, and burnout, especially during the first 5 years of education which is known as "the vulnerability period," during which 40–50% of teachers quit their job (Gallant and Riley, 2014). This may happen due to a high workload, limited support, fear of challenges, lack of time management, and lack of knowledge about controlling students' behaviors and satisfying their needs (Kelly et al., 2018).

In the contrary, the view of resilience as the capacity of an individual teacher to harness personal and contextual resources to navigate through challenges, as well as the dynamic process whereby characteristics of individual teachers and their personal and professional contexts interact over time as teachers use particular strategies, to enable the outcome of a teacher who experiences professional engagement and growth, commitment, enthusiasm, satisfaction, and well-being (Magno, et al. 2016).

Table 6

Level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers According to Social Environment

Social Environment Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. <u>have the ability to</u> relate easily to different age groups.	4.51	Very high level
2. have some mentors to guide and assist me in my day-to-day endeavor.	4.26	High level
3. can welcome a newcomer with open arms.	4.64	Very high level
4. can maintain quality time with my coworkers, friends, family, and others.	4.52	Very high level
5. <u>can</u> work objectively with my coworkers.	4.55	Very high level
6. <u>can</u> freely express my feelings and thoughts with my co-teachers.	4.43	High level
7. can establish good relationships with my superiors.	4.54	Very high level
Overall Mean	4.49	High level

Table 6 shows the resiliency of the Junior High School teachers according to Social Environment. The overall mean obtained is 4.49, which is interpreted as a "high level." It shows that five out of seven items obtained mean scores, which indicate "very high level," and the remaining two obtained mean scores, which indicate "high level" in terms of Social Environment.

Item no. 3, "I can welcome a newcomer with open arms," obtained the highest mean score of 4.64, which is interpreted as "very high level," In contrast, item no. 2, "I have some mentors to guide and assist me in my day-to-day endeavor," obtained a mean score of 4.26, which is interpreted as "high level."

This implies that in school, teachers need mentors to guide and support them in their everyday endeavors. Seasoned teachers can influence newcomer teachers to be resilient and confident when facing daily tasks.

This further implies that mentorship provides teachers, especially novices, with the knowledge and skills to manage classrooms, implement effective teaching strategies, and handle student needs. A mentor can offer practical advice, modeling, and constructive feedback, accelerating professional growth (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

Mentorship offers teachers not only guidance and support but also the opportunity to develop essential skills and refine their instructional practices. This relationship is particularly beneficial in navigating the complexities of teaching, building confidence, and improving classroom effectiveness, which highlights that a supportive and inclusive social environment is vital to developing and sustaining teachers' resiliency, making them better equipped to adapt, innovate, and thrive in challenging circumstances (Tait, M. 2008).

Table 7
Level of Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers

Grade Level	Mean	Interpretation
A	4.49	Very Satisfactory
B	4.33	Very Satisfactory
C	4.26	Very Satisfactory
D	4.15	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.31	Very Satisfactory

Table 7 shows the Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers. The overall mean obtained is 4.31, which is interpreted as "very satisfactory." It also indicates that Grade level A obtained the highest mean score of 4.49, interpreted as "very satisfactory," and grade level D obtained the lowest mean score of 4.15, interpreted also as "very satisfactory."

This suggests that the JHS teachers are able to perform their duties effectively despite the presence of challenges in their work. This indicates that teachers' work performance is determined by their contribution to the attainment of educational goals and objectives. However, in certain research, it is only measured based on their teaching conduct (Bashir, Alias, Saleh, & Halizah, 2017). Teachers' work effectiveness extends beyond the classroom or school and includes all environments where learners are present. The job performance of teachers has multiple dimensions. The dimensions encompassed in this study include lesson preparation, instructional techniques, student evaluation, commitment, extracurricular activities, effective monitoring and inspection, effective leadership, motivation and discipline, instructional, professional and personal qualities (Ali & Haider, 2017); contextual and task performance (Yusoff, Ali, & Khan, 2014); classroom management, considering individual differences among students, using motivational tools continuously, teaching style and methods, finding solutions to students' problems and guidance (Mehmood, Qasim, & Azam, 2013).

Additionally, the study examines contextual and task performance, classroom management, consideration of individual differences among students, continuous use of motivational tools, teaching style and methods, and the ability to find solutions to students' problems and provide guidance.

According to the study by Batangas (2022), it was analyzed that educational attainment and the number of training attended were significant factors affecting teaching performance. However, teaching position and teaching experience were determined insignificant factors. It can be regarded that teachers with higher educational attainment tend to perform better in teaching. If teachers are well-versed and in-depth knowledge of their field, it is expected that they have high performance. Similarly, the more training teachers attend, the better their performance. Generally, attaining higher education and attending training improve teaching quality performance.

Table 8
Relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy and level of Resiliency of Junior High School Teachers

Correlation	N	r	Sig. level	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Self-Efficacy	98	0.838	0.01	0.000	Significant
Level of Resiliency	98				

The data in Table 8 summarizes the relationship between the level of self-efficacy and resiliency of Junior High School teachers.

This data highlighted the relationship between the teachers' self-efficacy and resiliency level. The positive and high r - value signifies a direct relationship. Meaning the self-efficacy of teachers has significant impact to his/her resiliency. The p - value of 0.000 is lower to the alpha value 0.05, the hypothesis that says "there is no significant relationship in the respondents' level of self-efficacy and the level of resiliency is rejected.

The correlation between self-efficacy and resiliency significantly impacts the Junior High School teachers' overall professional well-being and effectiveness. High self-efficacy teachers typically have confidence in their capacity to overcome challenges and find workable solutions. This belief can directly increase their resilience when confronted with difficult teaching circumstances. Teachers are more likely to persevere through challenges rather than discourage or burn out. Hodges and Kimmons (2020) found that self-efficacy positively correlated with resilience, particularly among novice teachers. Teachers with strong self-belief in their abilities were more likely to persist in the profession, even in challenging environments. This study underscores how early career experiences can shape both self-efficacy and resilience.

Antonio (2023) indicates that teachers' resilience and self-efficacy are positively correlated. According to a study that looked at Filipino teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic, those with higher self-efficacy levels were also more resilient. This implies that having faith in one's ability to educate improves one's ability to handle and adjust to difficulties. Moreover, teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to use successful coping mechanisms in the face of stress. By being proactive, they not only lessen the effects of stress but also strengthen their resilience, which allows them to continue performing well under duress (Marilou F. Paller, Erlinda A. Quirap, 2024).

Table 9
Relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy and the level of Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers

Correlation	N	r_s	Sig. level	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Self-Efficacy	98	0.312	0.01	0.002	Significant
Level of Teachers' Job Performance	98				

The data in Table 9 summarizes the relationship between the level of self-efficacy and level of teachers' job performance of Junior High School teachers.

This highlighted self-efficacy and the level of teachers' job performance. The positive and high r - value signifies a direct relationship. Meaning the self-efficacy of teachers has significant factor to his/her performance. The p - value of 0.002 is lower to the alpha value 0.05, the hypothesis that says "there is no significant relationship in the respondents' level of self-efficacy and the level of job performance is rejected.

The findings that a significant relationship exists between teachers' self-efficacy and job performance have meaningful implications for educational policy, professional development, and school leadership.

An educator is considered one of the most significant individuals in charge of determining the future of a country. According to the review, schools need to focus more on raising teachers' job satisfaction and self-efficacy levels by examining and strengthening the elements that support these outcomes. The current review also details tools for assessing teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction. The review demonstrates the favorable relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and their efficacy (Gkolia et al., 2014).

According to the Department of Education (2017), in today's continuously growing diversity of students in the classroom, including higher accountability standards, teachers in the present era may find their jobs even more challenging. For instance, implementing the K-12 reform, also known as the R.A. 10533 in 2013, has changed the landscape of teacher quality requirements in the Philippines. Specifically, the education reform process warrants an equivalent supportive focus on teacher quality - high-quality teachers who are properly equipped and prepared to assume the roles and functions of a K to 12 teacher. While there seem to be various attributes that could significantly contribute to teacher quality, teacher efficacy is one of the most important beliefs that have received considerable attention in influencing both student and teacher outcomes in the education context (Bituin & Dacanay, 2018).

Enhancing teachers' self-efficacy through targeted professional development programs could improve their job performance. Schools should foster supportive work environments where teachers feel valued and equipped to succeed. The study suggests that enhancing job satisfaction through supportive supervision and job security can lead to improved teacher performance (Baluyos, Rivera, & Baluyos, 2019).

The conviction of the influence of personal actions or efforts on achieving goals or objectives is one's notion of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy all does to an individual's belief in their capacity to execute tasks effectively through the application of their skills or activities. Low self-efficacy fosters adverse emotions regarding one's capabilities and

accountability for personal performance. A strong sense of self-efficacy fosters the belief that an individual is accountable for their own fate and capable of achieving their desires.

The findings were supported by the study of Craig (2018), which reported that a truly positive school climate is not characterized simply by the absence of gangs, violence, or discipline problems, but also by the presence of a set of norms and values that focus everyone's attention on what is most important and motivate them to work hard toward a common purpose.

Table 10

Relationship between the level of resiliency and level of Teachers' Performance of Junior High School Teacher

Correlation	N	r	Sig. level	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Resiliency	98				
Level of Teachers' Performance	98	0.299	0.01	0.003	Significant

The data in Table 43 summarizes the relationship between the level of resiliency and level of teachers' performance of Junior High School teachers.

The positive and high r – value signifies a direct relationship. Meaning the level of resiliency of teachers has significant factor to his/her teaching performance. The p – value of 0.003 is lower to the alpha value 0.05, therefore there is significant and high relationship. The hypothesis that stated that there is no significant relationship between the level of Resiliency and Job Performance of Junior High School Teachers, is therefore rejected.

This implies that the schools and educational institutions may need to invest in programs aimed at enhancing teachers' resiliency. Workshops on stress management, emotional regulation, and coping strategies could help improve resiliency, thereby positively impacting job performance.

The finding of a significant difference between resiliency and job performance highlights the importance of fostering a work culture and institutional practices that prioritize teacher well-being. These implications can guide schools and policymakers in implementing evidence-based interventions to enhance both resiliency and professional outcomes.

Ebersohn (2014) emphasized that teacher resilience is an important area of study because teachers who do a good job and stay in the field have a positive impact on their students' learning. Furthermore, Gratacos et al. (2021) solidify that teacher resilience sees itself as a concept that bridges the gap between the complicated contexts of practice and the people who work in them.

Conclusions:

The study found that junior high school teachers, mostly older females with longer service tenure and higher household income, demonstrated strong self-efficacy in instructional delivery, skills development, and behavior modification, along with high resiliency in managing work environments, attitudinal concerns, and social interactions. Their collaborative skills, leadership, and professionalism contributed to their effectiveness, with significant differences in self-efficacy and resiliency based on sex and family income. A positive correlation was identified between self-efficacy, resiliency, and job performance, emphasizing their interconnected impact on teaching effectiveness. The study recommends fostering a positive attitude, adaptability, and openness to feedback among teachers, while the Department of Education should develop resources and training modules to enhance competence. Curriculum and school governance divisions should prioritize technical assistance, workshops, and systematic performance assessments. Public Schools District Supervisors should support teacher skills development through career guidance and research, while school administrators should implement professional development plans and self-evaluation strategies. Teachers are encouraged to pursue further studies and explore innovative teaching methods to enhance their effectiveness and student outcomes.

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